

Imbalance between Schema and Dynamic Equivalence: An Analysis of the C-E Translation of Profile of Air China

Yali CHENG¹

¹*School of English for International Business, Guangdong University of Foreign Studies, Guangzhou, China, E-mail: 20200310011@gdufs.edu.cn*

Abstract

Schema is a concept from cognitive poetics, a complete information system composed of correlative knowledge. Dynamic equivalence theory proposed by Eugene A. Nida is a precise translation theory centered on reader's reception. This paper synthesizes schema theory with theories in dynamic equivalence, based on which the author constructs a framework for analyzing the translation process of the profile of Air China (CA), revealing some existing problems and appealing for the specific strategies for the translation of CA's profile. This paper concludes that in the C-E translation of CA, there exist imbalances between the schemata and dynamic equivalences, namely from the perspectives of language, content and culture. It is hoped that some constructive attention and promising improvement are generated for CA's English profile or even for other enterprises' profiles.

Keywords: schema theory, dynamic equivalence theory, C-E translation of Chinese airline profiles, Air China (CA)

1. Introduction

For an airways, in addition to providing products¹ and services, it also needs to publicize itself through proper channels in order to raise its international popularity and prestige in markets at home and abroad. In addition, as the universal language, English exerts a crucial impact on international communication and commercial intercourse. Under this circumstance, the C-E translation of Chinese airline profiles, usually acts as an information window, the highly condensed content of the company, often presenting the most valuable information to the target audience (Li, 2021). Airline profiles to some extent decide the very first impression of an enterprise to foreigners. However, many Chinese airlines are devoid of attention to the English translation of their corporate profiles, ignoring crucial factors that should be delicately handled. As such, decent C-E translations of Chinese airline profiles are necessary and insightful, which is conducive to the enhancement of airline's images, and in turn, in regard to the airline profile, it involves a wide scope with high value of translation. The C-E translation of Chinese airline profiles in this study is under the guidance of schema theory and dynamic equivalence theory.

Firstly, schema is a concept from cognitive poetics, represents the presentation form of knowledge which systematically associates the new information with the given information for the purpose of information storage and processing; it is a complete information system composed of correlative knowledge (Liu & Zhao, 2014).

Secondly, dynamic equivalence theory proposed by Eugene A. Nida (1986) is a precise translation theory centered on reader's reception (Du, 2019). Nida's dynamic equivalence theory is universally acknowledged as the commonly applied translation theory to achieve the linguistic, content and cultural equivalence between the source text (ST) and the target text (TT) due to its focus on accurate transformation of ST's cultural connotations instead of the rigid superficial translation, which has been highly valued and influenced China's translation practice.

This paper will synthesize schema theory in cognitive poetics with theories in dynamic equivalence, based on which the author attempts to construct a framework for analyzing the translation process of CA's profile (ST), try to propose some existing problems of profile's translation (TT) and explore the specific strategies for them, hoping that some constructive suggestions could be provided for the references of CA's profile or even for other enterprises' profiles.

2. Literature Review

This part is an overview of previous studies on translation of company profile from the angles of schema theory and from dynamic equivalence theory as well as from other perspectives.

2.1 Studies on Translation of Company Profiles from the Angle of Schema Theory

¹ The product of civil aviation is space transfer (displacement) of passengers and goods.

Milton (1999) regards corporate profile as an effective tool to win potential customers' trust and to make a good impression on them by giving a brief introduction of who you are and what you do. Generally speaking, a corporate profile seems as a bridge between a company and its customers or potential customers, and it is clear that the function on a whole is to inform, to promote and finally to persuade favorable responses from the target readers (Jiang, 2014). Therefore, how to translate their profiles as the ST (Chinese) to meet the stylistic requirements of the TT (English) and achieve the promotional objective become a common concern for companies and business translators (Liu, 2012).

The word "schema" (plural: schemata) is from the Greek vocabulary² and is firstly put forward by the German philosopher Immanuel Kant in 1781 in his famous work *Critique of Pure Reason*. According to Kant, new concept could become meaningful only when it has been connected with one's existing knowledge (Cui, 2002: 53). According to Bartlett, the term "schema" refers to an active organization of past reactions, or of past experience, which must always be supposed to be operating in any well-adapted organic response" (Bartlett, 1932: 201). Since this paper is mainly about the translation of airline profiles from the angle of schema theory, contents as follow will conduct a more detailed literature review about it.

Li (2014) explores the application of schema theory in the progress of business translation and discusses the relation between business translation and the four forms of schema theory, namely, linguistic schema, content schema, structural schema and cultural schema. However, the study is too general to reveal the relevance to specific company issues, such as the translation of company profile, translation of company contracts, etc.

Fortunately, there are still some valuable studies concerning company profiles under the guidance of schema theory. For example, Qiao (2014) conducts a comparative study on schemata of corporate profiles about the Chinese companies and the British and American ones, which discovers that they have both similarities and differences of schemata in their corporate profiles at three levels: language schemata, cultural schemata and formal schemata (Qiao, 2014). Although Qiao's study, to some extent, will help Chinese companies create corporate profiles which can be comprehended and recalled more easily by the foreign readers, her analysis is only limited to analyzing the schema similarities and differences between Chinese, British and American company profiles. As such, detailed suggestions on improving the translation and writing of corporate profiles ought to be proposed on the basis of the study. Besides, it will be better if the study is carried out with more data.

Four years later, Li (2018) interprets English profiles of Chinese and American telecommunication companies based on schema theory. Li analyzes 60 corporate English profiles in China and the U.S. from the aspects of linguistic schema, formal schema, content schema and schema activation so as to find out the similarities and differences between the two and to interpret the differences from the cognitive and social-cultural perspectives. This paper can shed some light on the study of applying schema theory to corporate profiles and provide some implications for Chinese telecommunication companies. However, it is devoid of discussion of detailed translation methods and strategies for Chinese companies to create high-quality English profiles.

As what Yan (2019) reveals in her review of cultural schemata theory in China from 2000 to 2018, most of these studies are repetitive, and the proposed translation methods are based on the translation strategies and methods proposed by previous scholars, lacking innovation; in terms of research methods, many authors only cite relevant examples, lacking in-depth discussions and explanations, which should be avoided in future studies (Yan, 2019).

In short, schema theory has been extensively applied in various domains in domestic studies, but at present, those studies which apply schema theory mainly concentrates on conventional methods, frameworks or strategies, which are devoid of innovation. In addition, papers analyzing the company abound, but few of which specifically focus on company profiles, not mention to airline profiles. Besides, some current research on C-E translation of company profiles is disconnected from prevalent guiding theories, remaining only in the level of theoretical introduction rather than concrete application of theory and practice. There are apparent research gap in study of translation of company profiles by combining schema theory with other theories like dynamic equivalence theory. Therefore, it is of great necessity and significance to fill the research gap of corporate profile translation by finding new theoretical guidance.

2.2 Studies on Translation of Company Profiles Based on Dynamic Equivalence Theory

² Greek *skhēma* meant 'form, figure'. Latin took it over as *schēma* and used it as the equivalent of figure in a range of applications, such as 'figure of speech' and 'diagram', many of which were originally taken over by English. Source: <https://www.quword.com/etym/s/scheme> [accessed on November 28th, 2021]

In this part, studies on dynamic equivalence theory are first introduced and then previous studies on company profile from the perspective of dynamic equivalence theory and other perspectives will be reviewed.

The definition of dynamic equivalence is firstly given by Nida in his book *Toward a Science of the Translation*. In this book, based on the experience in biblical translation, Nida put forward two translation approaches: dynamic equivalence and formal equivalence. Dynamic equivalence advocates that “the relationship between receptor and language should be substantially the same as that which existed between the original receptors and the message” (Nida, 1964: 159). While formal equivalence pays attention to translating the meanings of words and phrases in a more literal way so as to keep literal fidelity. Nida also emphasizes the priority of dynamic equivalence over formal equivalence.

Dynamic equivalence is the quality of a translation in which “the receptors of the message in the receptor language respond to it in substantially the same manner as the receptors in the source language” (Nida, 1969: 24). It is wildly spread and gradually gains wide acceptance. Furthermore, dynamic equivalence not only applies the research results of linguistics to the practice of translation but also provides a linguistic theory of translation for researchers and is of referential significance to translators (Zhu, 2020).

This paper prefers Nida’s dynamic equivalence, because the essence of this theory is found to correspond with the characteristics of translation in C-E translation of Chinese airline profiles. The detailed analysis will be presented in the following parts. Because dynamic equivalence theory (also functional equivalence theory) originates the guidance of translation, research on translation based on it is abundant especially in China. However, the author finds that prevalent studies on Chinese airline profiles are scarce. Next, some crucial studies on company profiles under the guidance of dynamic equivalence will be reviewed.

Liu et al. (2014) analyzes the differences between Chinese and foreign profiles of some well-known large companies, trying to use the strategy of discourse reconstruction to solve these differences based on Nida’s dynamic theory. They argue that it is necessary to reconstruct the discourse in the progress of translation according to the readers’ requirements, so that the functional equivalence can be achieved and the final purpose of the company profile can be realized.

Zheng (2021) takes the C-E translation of export-oriented company profiles in Liaoning Province as an example to analyze the problems encountered in the C-E translation of company profiles and the strategies used in translation. He draws conclusions that the current translation quality is uneven, and there are problems in the C-E translation of company profiles such as improper translation, logical confusion, which affect the image and publicity effect of the company. Additionally, due to differences in culture, thinking styles, expression habits, writing styles, there are many differences in content, words, syntax, and culture in Chinese and English company profiles. In the process of achieving functional equivalence, methods such as restructuring, shifting, and omission methods can be used to make the translation more suitable for the target language reader’s habits (Zheng, 2021). Zheng collects profiles of some export-oriented companies in Liaoning Province from their official website. As what he acknowledges in the end of the paper, the authenticity of these corpora is beyond doubt. Thus, this paper still needs to be improved and further research needs to be done on this subject.

Apart from export-oriented company profiles, studies on other companies’ profiles are also in full swing. Fu et al. (2021) compare the differences between the English profiles of British and American e-commerce companies (Walmart, Asda, Onbuy, etc.) and Chinese e-commerce companies (Alibaba, Qidian, Jingdong, etc.), discussing the translation problems of Chinese e-commerce companies’ profiles and proposing the causes and corresponding solutions. According to their findings, the translation of e-commerce company profiles on the basis of functional equivalence is not only the conversion between forms and contents, but also the communication between cultures (Fu, et al., 2021). Therefore, when translating company profiles, the translator should pay attention to the reading response of the target readers, deeply understand the culture of the ST, and adopt the method of translation, change the person, increase the content and adjust the structure to meet the reading habits of the target readers, so that the English company profile can be translated smoothly.

2.3 Studies on Translation of Company Profile from Other Perspectives

After searching for studies on company profiles, the author gains two results: Firstly, these studies almost use only one theory to conduct the research. Despite the fact that those studies have somewhat refined the previous studies, they still lack multifaceted analyses and interdisciplinary perspectives. Secondly, studies on company profiles is increasingly popular, but those focusing on airline profiles are insufficient. For example, Xu (2020) explores the problems in the English translation of tea company profiles under the guidance of Newmark’s communicative translation theory (1981: 22). It is proposed that tea company profile translation ought to give priority to the acceptance level of English readers and fully consider the

differences in Chinese and English language and thinking styles. Also, Tan (2021) makes a report on C-E translation of profile of Zhengzhou Yutong Bus CO., Ltd in the light of communicative translation theory.

Based on German functionalist translation theory, Gao (2019) compares and analyzes two groups of pharmaceutical company profile in China and abroad. The results show that there are significant differences between the two groups in terms of length, information distribution, high-frequency vocabulary and genre characteristics. Therefore, translators need to adjust the structure of the English translation of the profiles according to the information needs and reading habits of Western audiences (Gao, & Ma, 2019).

Form the perspectives of Aristotle's "Three Appeals Theory", Perelman and Olbrechts' Audience Theory and Presence Theory, Li (2020) takes Huawei company profile as an example to explore the positive role of rhetorical persuasion in the selection of translation strategies and construction of translated texts in enterprise's international publicity, aiming to help enterprises realize effective persuasion and increase their influence.

Besides, there are scholars absorbed in other theories to analyze company profiles, such as Verschueren's Adaption Theory³ (Wu, 2009 & Jin, 2011), Geert Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory⁴ (Li, 2013). Also, Shi Chunrang conducts a corpus-based study on the translation of Chinese enterprise profiles (Shi, et al., 2012). Such examples abound.

However, the author deems that whatever theories are used to study company profiles, most of the subjects studied in these results are too general. That is, if the research subject is expanded to company profiles, then the reference value is not sufficiently targeted when facing companies with different types and nature. This paper focuses on a detailed subject, airlines in China, to study the dynamic equivalence problems in the C-E translation based on schema theory, striving to enhance the innovation and relevance values of company profile research.

3. Theoretical Framework

This part contains a general introduction of the relevant concepts in schema theory and dynamic equivalence, on the basis of which a synthetic framework of analysis will be constructed and further explained.

3.1 The Categories of Schema Theory

3.1.1 Linguistic Schema

Carrell (1983: 79) puts forward that "linguistic schemata include knowledge of letters and their corresponding sounds, grammar, vocabulary, idioms, word attack skills, and distinctions between spoken and written forms of the language". That's to say, knowledge of contexts or language can activate schemata stored in people's mind when they encounter a new discourse. Translation is a process of decoding (understanding) and coding (expression). As a translator, he or she is first and foremost a reader (Yan, 2016: 26). Good translation can only be generated when the translator masters both the ST and the TT, thus it could be possible to decode the ST and construct comparative schema to encode the TT in a proper way.

3.1.2 Content Schema

Content schema refers to one's background knowledge of the content area of the text and it contains both specific and general information in the given topic (Carrel & Eisterhold, 1983: 79), which exerts a crucial influence on translators to understand the ST. Kern makes a more detailed explanation for content schema: it is related to the cultural concept, the topical knowledge and the extent of readers' understanding about the world (Kern, 2000). Linguistic schema is the first step to comprehend the ST, while content schema makes compensation for the inadequacy of previous understandings, helping translators well master the ST and generate more perfect TT.

3.1.3 Cultural Schema

Numerous scholars around the world have defined cultural schema. According to Garro (2010), cultural schema is related to the cultural knowledge beyond the text, the generalized collection of customs, tradition, folklore etc., which is a cultural knowledge structure in people's mind concerning the past experience. George Yule states that cultural schema refers to previous knowledge structures based on experience in a particular culture (Sun, 2015: 14). Specializing in the research on

³ A linguistic theory created by Jef Verschueren, a leading Belgian linguist and Secretary General of the International Pragmatics Society.

⁴ Hofstede's cultural dimension theory is a framework proposed by Geert Hofstede, a Dutch psychologist, to measure cultural differences among different countries.

the application of schemata to translation, Liu (2003) maintains that cultural schema is the knowledge structural chunk about culture existing in people's brain, or it is an organizational model of the knowledge of culture based on previous experience, which can be mobilized to perceive and understand various cultural phenomena in the world.

In a word, besides the translation process, cultural schemata can be used in diverse areas and they are dynamic with many differences, but there are also commonalities which can be learned through efforts. Thus, cultural schemata can be compensated in one way or another.

3.2 Dynamic Equivalence in Translation

Nida (1969) once said that the purpose of translation is to achieve the closest equivalence between the ST and the TT, which is also important in the process of C-E translation of airline profiles. Furthermore, the surface structure of the ST needs to be divided into the basic elements of the deep structure⁵; these are "transferred" in the translation process and then "restructured" semantically and stylistically into the surface structure of the TT (See the *Figure 3.2*).

Figure 3.2: Nida's Three-Stage System of translation (from Nida and Taber, 1969: 33)

Next, for the sake of better guidance for the C-E translation of Chinese airlines, the author carries out a detailed analysis of equivalence from the perspectives of language, content and culture, aiming to make an instructive connection to the three corresponding schemata mentioned in the section 3.1 (linguistic, content and cultural).

3.2.1 Linguistic Equivalence

According to the author, both the semantic and stylistic concepts belong to the category of language, so semantic equivalence and stylistic equivalence mentioned above are collectively referred to as linguistic equivalence. Semantic equivalence is the most fundamental and important principle in translation, which requires the translator to pay attention to the grammatical and semantic relationships between words, phrases and sentences. In other words, in order to achieve semantic equivalence, translators are expected to pay attention to the lexical levels as well as syntactical ones; as for stylistic equivalence, it is defined as functional equivalence among the source text and translated text, aiming at achieving consistent expression by the use of invariant with the same meaning (Nida, 1969). Usually, parallel clauses are used in Chinese airline profiles, and they are antithetical and neat, which may cause translation challenges for both translators and target readers. To achieve stylistic equivalence, translators can adopt literal translation method under the guidance of dynamic equivalence theory.

3.2.2 Content Equivalence

Nida (1969) believes that translation ought to firstly adhere to the content equivalence and then form equivalence. Content equivalence is not strictly word-to-word or word-to-sentence equivalence. Therefore, in the process of translation, the translator should focus on the meaning and spirit of the original text, instead of sticking to the linguistic structure of the original text, that is, not sticking to formal correspondence. When translating the Chinese airline profiles, the translator cannot only analyze the language itself but put the language into a specific context to analyze its meaning and function. As

⁵ Some of Nida's systematic approaches borrow theoretical concepts and terminology both from semantics and pragmatics and from Noam Chomsky's work on syntactic structure which formed the theory of a universal generative-transformation grammar.

such, Nida proposes a number of tweaks, such as adding notes or footnotes. In order to make the readers of the target text can react similarly to the readers of the original text, the translator should fully consider the needs of the target readers for understanding and appreciation, and select annotations suitable for the specific context.

3.2.3 Cultural Equivalence

Language is an essential and important part of a given culture and that the impact of culture upon a given language is something intrinsic and indispensable. When it is used in contexts of communications, it is bound up with culture in multiple and complex ways. As is known, the relationship between language and culture exerts great impact on translation, in which case, translation is the replacement of textual material in one language by equivalent textual material in another language, so the process of translation at least gets involved two different cultures. In terms of the cultural difference in translation, the equivalence between Chinese and English can be categorized into total equivalence, near equivalence, little equivalence and non-equivalence (Wang, 2016).

3.3 Analytical Framework for the Present Study

Since this paper is based on schema theory and dynamic equivalence theory, the Figure 3.4 synthesizes both of them to illustrate the analytical process. The detailed processes and illustrations are as follow.

Figure 3.3: Analytical model of translation process Based on Schema Theory and Dynamic Equivalence Theory for Present Study

Firstly, the schemata starts from the writer of the ST who can transfer his/her schemata in the mind into the texts, otherwise the ST and the later TT (translation) will not be generated. Secondly, the translator ought to make a contrastive analysis of the schemata embodied in the ST and TT from the angles of language, content and culture, thus activating the corresponding ST schemata and encoding them into the texts of TT (translation). Meanwhile, the transformation of dynamic equivalence between the ST and TT need finishing. Thirdly, based on the TT, translators should regard themselves as the target readers or find some real ones, trying to encode the TT in the most appropriate way to construct TT schemata which can achieve the highest degree of schemata transformation from ST to TT.

4. Discussion and Results

In the light of the *Figure 3.3*, the author will go through the following three steps to interpret the translation process. Firstly, decoding the ST and activating the ST schemata from language, content and culture; secondly, comparing the ST and TT and actively constructing the schemata of the TT; thirdly, verifying the accomplishment of dynamic equivalences between the schemata of ST and TT and polishing the TT again. Next, some specific examples from the profile of CA⁶ will be analyzed based on these three steps.

Table 4.1: Five Examples Cited from the Profile of CA

	ST	TT
Example 1	国航的企业标识由一只艺术化的凤凰和中国改革开放的总设计师邓小平同志书写的“中国国际航空公司”以及英文“CA”构成。	The design also features the calligraphic version of CA's Chinese name, a reproduction of the handwriting by late Chinese leader Deng Xiaoping, the architect of China's drastic social and economic transformation who laid the foundation for the country's economic power.
Example 2	“凤凰”是中华民族远古传说中的祥瑞之鸟，为百鸟之王。	The corporate logo of CA depicts phoenix, a legendary bird worshiped by the nation since ancient times as a symbol of luck and happiness.
Example 3	标志颜色为中国传统的大红，造型以简洁舞动的线条展现凤凰姿态，同时又是英文“VIP”（尊贵客人）的艺术变形。	With imagination stretched a bit, the way the logo is laid out recalls the English word “VIP”. The deep red color is used since it's associated with anything happy and lucky in Chinese culture.
Example 4	“凤凰者，仁鸟也”，“见则天下宁”，凤凰“出于东方君子之国，翱翔四海之外”，擷英咀华，志存高远。	Chinese ancient literature contains constant references to the bird which “flies from the eastern Happy Land over mountains and seas and bestows luck and happiness upon all parts of the world”.
Example 5	国航愿景是“全球领先的航空公司”，使命是“安全第一，四心服务，稳健发展，成就员工，履行责任”，品牌定位是“专业信赖，国际品质，中国风范”。	Our vision is to become “A leading carrier in the world”. Our mission stresses “operational safety, customer orientation, steady growth, people development and fulfillment of responsibilities”. Our brand positioning is to be “a professional, trusted, internationally respected Chinese brand closely associated with China”.

Step 1: Decoding and activating the ST schemata.

As is shown, from the angles of language, these four examples are full of long, compound sentences and four-word structure words, making information detailed and understandable, such as Example 1 (国航的企业标识由一只艺术化的凤凰和.....构成) and Example 5 (安全第一、专业信赖.....国际品质、中国风范). A series of four-character structures also make the ST symmetric, vivid, full of vigor and rhythmic beauty. However, the contents are connected to Chinese history and legend, and the time span of context is large, from ancient legend to modern society such as Example 4 (凤凰者，仁鸟也，见则天下宁) and Example 5 (国航愿景是.....国际品质，中国风范), so the understandings and schemata of the ST become harder to decode. Furthermore, from the angle of culture, there are a large amount of research value in the ST.

Step 2: Comparing the ST and TT and constructing the schemata of the TT.

Table 4.2: Analyzing Translated Texts

Three Angles	Comparative Schemata

⁶ Sources: http://www.airchina.com.cn/cn/about_us/company.shtml & http://www.airchina.com.cn/en/about_us/company.shtml

	ST (Chinese)	TT (English)
Linguistic	<p>(1) Chinese emphasizes the implicit coherence of sentences without fixed grammar or syntactic format.</p> <p>(2) The text is sometimes compact but sometimes scattered.</p> <p>(3) In the ST, the modern vernacular and ancient Chinese can be switched flexibly.</p>	<p>(1) English pays attention to syntactic structures and their explicit cohesion.</p> <p>(2) The text is scattered.</p> <p>(3) In the TT, modern English is universally used.</p>
Content	<p>(1) Contents cited from classical quotes make meaning more difficult to be decoded.</p> <p>(2) The time span of context in the ST is large, from ancient legend to modern society.</p>	<p>(1) In the TT, the content schemata of Chinese classical quotes are elusive.</p> <p>(2) The time span of context in the TT is disordered, from ancient legend to modern society and then to the past century.</p>
Cultural	Expressions related to distinctive Chinese history, myths and legends have frequently occurred.	The TT is devoid of expressions or explanations about Chinese history, myths and legends.

From the aspect of linguistic equivalence, the sentences in the ST usually have no obvious conjunctions and the content structure is fragmented; while sentences in the TT have complete subject-verb-object with compact and complete structure. In Example 3, although the ST lacks a detailed subject, it is understandable that the logo of airline, or the phoenix is illustrated with reference to the context, which emphasizes the implicit coherence of sentences without fixed grammar or syntactic format. In the TT, however, sentences must have complete subject-verb-object with compact and complete structure to make the meaning clear and readable.

From the perspective of content equivalence, the TT fails to achieve the correspondence of meaning with the ST. For instance, in Example 3, “造型以简洁舞动的线条展现凤凰姿态” is translated as “With imagination stretched a bit”. The concept of “imagination stretched a bit” is extremely vague and the translation is somewhat arbitrary, breaking the content equivalence. Also, “艺术变形” in the ST cannot find the translated meaning in the TT.

From the angle of cultural equivalence, there exist cultural defaults by comparing the ST and TT because the translation version cannot provide reasonable and readable connotations of the ST. For example, in Example 4, “仁鸟” has neither a counterpart nor an interpretation in the TT; “东方君子之国” is translated as “eastern Happy Land”, but how “君子之国” can be connected to “Happy Land”? It contains a cultural default here. Also, “撷英咀华” in Chinese refers to selecting the essence, but there is no corresponding expression in the TT. Such cultural defaults abound in the C-E translation of the profile of CA.

Step 3: Verifying the accomplishment of dynamic equivalences between the schemata of ST and TT and polishing the TT again.

Based on the linguistic equivalence, the author deems that the schemata of ST and TT fail to accomplish linguistic equivalence in the fields of the word-selection, syntax, text order and style. For instance, “中国改革开放的总设计师” in Example 1 is translated as “the architect of China’s drastic social and economic transformation”, breaking the semantic equivalence and leading target readers to the domain of architecture or a social revolution, which is far from the original definition. In fact, there is a proper noun to express “中国改革开放” in English, that’s “China’s reform and opening-up”. Thus, personally speaking, the TT of “中国改革开放的总设计师” can be better translated as “the chief architect of China’s reform and opening up”.

Similarly, the schemata of ST and TT exist content equivalence problems in terms of meaning, spirit, as well as context, and the cultural equivalence is little accomplished. For instance, Example 2, the ST “中华民族远古传说中的祥瑞之鸟” is translated as “a legendary bird worshiped by the nation since ancient times as a symbol of luck and happiness”, which breaks the content and cultural equivalences. Because on the one hand, the word “中华民族” lacks equivalent translation, and it is not specified which country this is. On the other hand, the translation of “祥瑞之鸟” is inaccurate, missing the cultural connotations. In Chinese, “祥瑞” refers to “something auspicious”, a sign of good fortune. It is considered by

Confucianism to be a natural phenomenon that expresses the will of heaven and is beneficial to human beings. Thus, “祥瑞” contains the connotation of oneness of heaven and humans and it cannot simply translated as “a symbol of luck and happiness” What’s worse, “百鸟之王” is devoid of corresponding translation in the TT. In summary, from the perspective of authors, Example 2 can be better translated as “Phoenix, the king of birds, is the auspicious bird in the ancient legend of the Chinese nation”.

By and large, the company profile of CA suffers from a series of translation problems, concentrating on the imbalance among the schemata of ST, the schemata of TT, and dynamic equivalences. Thus, some translation strategies is necessary for CA.

According to the contents above, strategies for solving the problems in the C-E translation of A's profiles can be provided from the perspectives of language, content and culture. Firstly, from the linguistic angle, translators are expected to have a good command of linguistic features and differences of the source language and the target language, trying to activate the schemata based on the corresponding linguistic habits, such as the text, grammar, syntax and style. Secondly, in addition to the language abilities, translators ought to possess abundant knowledge as well as excellent competence of sorting and interpreting information, because rich knowledge accumulation and sufficient practice are conducive to the process of schemata adjustment. Thirdly, on the level of culture, it is necessary for translators to strengthen and deepen the understanding of different culture and customs, avoiding cultural prejudices and ambiguities, adding footnotes for opaque and elusive contents and omitting redundant contents.

5. Conclusion

Under modern circumstance, C-E translation is an indispensable bridge for communication and understanding between China and the world. Hence, scholars and translators are expected to find translation problems and spare no efforts to present more better and smooth translations. The paper provides an innovative analytical framework that allows more translation problems to be studied in the future. What’s more, this framework synthesizes schema theory and a series of dynamic equivalence rather than under a single theory. Therefore, for the future researches on C-E translation of company profiles or on other translation problems of company issues, it is hopefully applicable and feasible.

References

- Bartlett, C. (1932). *Remembering: a Study in Experimental and Social Psychology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cai, Y. (2018). 图式理论关照下旅游文本的生态翻译研究 [An Eco-translatological Study on Tourism Text Based on Schema Theory: With the C-E Translation of Guangzhou Scenic Spot Introductions as Case Analyses]. 硕士学位论文, 广东外语外贸大学 [Master’s paper in Guangdong University of Foreign Studies].
- Carrell, P. L. & Eisterhold, J. C. (1983). Schema Theory and ESL Reading Pedagogy. *TESOL Quarterly*, 17(4), 553-573.
- Chen, Y. (2013). 浅谈奈达的功能对等理论 [A Brief Discussion of Nida's Functional Equivalence Theory]. *青春岁月* [Youth Years], (16), 137
- Cui, Y. P. (2002). 图式理论在L2阅读理解中的运用 [The Application of Schema Theory in Second Language Reading]. *外语教学* [Foreign Language Education], (05), 52-57.
- Du, Y. N. (2019). 动态对等视角下《纸牌屋》字幕文化负载词翻译研究 [A Study on the E-C Translation of Subtitle Culture-loaded Expressions in House of Cards from the Perspective of Dynamic Equivalence]. 硕士学位论文, 西华大学. Master’s paper in Xihua University.
- Fu, X., Zheng, W., Lu, L. X. & An, R. X. (2021). 付筱, 郑雯, 陆立先 & 安锐霞.(2021). 中国电商公司简介英译调查研究. [A Study on English Translation of Chinese E-Commerce Company Profiles]. *海外英语* [Overseas English], (03), 162-163.
- Gao, Yun & Ma, Baiju. (2019). 功能主义视域下中医药公司简介英译问题与策略. [Problems and Strategies of English Translation of Chinese Medicine Company Profiles from the Perspective of Functionalist Translation Theory]. *中医药管理杂志* [Journal of Traditional Chinese Medicine Management], (16), 29-32.
- Garro, C. (2010). Remembering What One Knows and the Construction of the Past: A Comparison of Cultural Consensus Theory and Cultural Schema Theory. *Ethos*, 28(3), 275-319.
- Han, X. (2017). 图式理论在商务翻译中的应用研究 [The Application of Schema Theory in the Study of Business Translation]. 硕士学位论文, 南京师范大学 [Master’s paper in Nanjing Normal University].

- Jiang, Y. W. (2014). 功能主义目的论视角下中国本土航空公司简介的英译 [On C-E Translation of Corporate Profiles of Chinese Local Airlines from the Perspective of the Functionalist Approach]. 硕士学位论文, 吉林财经大学. [Master's paper in Jilin University of Finance & Economics].
- Kern, R. (2000). *Literacy and Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
- Li, B. J. (2018). 基于图式理论的中美通信公司英文简介对比研究 [A Comparative Study of English Profiles of Chinese and American Telecommunication Companies Based on Schema Theory]. 硕士学位论文, 广东外语外贸大学 [Master's paper in Guangdong University of Foreign Studies].
- Li, L. L. (2020). 修辞劝说视角下企业外宣翻译策略的分析——以华为官网的公司简介为例. [An Analysis of Translation Strategies in Enterprise International Publicity from the Perspectives of Rhetorical Persuasion: A Case Study of Huawei Company Profile]. 外文研究 [Foreign Studies], (01), 67-72+108.
- Liu, G. F., Jiang, T. W. & Huang, L. (2012). 中文公司简介英译中的语篇重构 [The Reconstruction of Discourse in the English Translation of Chinese Company Profiles]. 湖北函授大学学报 [Journal of Hubei Open Vocational College], 25(08): 130-132.
- Liu, W. & Zhao, Z. H. (2014). 认知诗学研究 [A Study on Cognitive Poetics]. 北京: 中国文史出版社 [Beijing: Chinese Cultural and Historical Press].
- Li, X. F. (2021). “一带一路” 视域下基于平行文本的企业简介翻译教学探讨. [Research on Translation Teaching of Enterprise's Profile Based on Parallel Text from the Perspective of “One Belt and One Road”]. 陕西教育(高教) [Shanxi Education], (07), 37-38.
- Li, Y. (2014). 认知图式理论在商务英语翻译中的应用研究. (eds.) [A Study on the Application of Cognitive Schema Theory in Business English Translation. (eds.)] 第四届全国认知语言学与二语习得学术研讨会会议文集 [Proceedings of the Fourth National Symposium on Cognitive Linguistics and Second Language Acquisition], 35-36.
- Nida, A. (1964). *Toward a Science of Translating*. Leiden: E.J.Brill.
- Nida, A. & Charles T. (1969). *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Leiden: E.J.Brill.
- Nida, A. (2004). *Toward a Science of Translating*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.
- Qiao, J. B. (2014). 基于图式理论的中国公司与英美公司简介对比分析 [A Schema-Based Comparative Study on Corporate Profiles of Chinese Companies and British and American Companies]. 硕士学位论文, 北京林业大学 [Master's paper in Beijing Forestry University].
- Shi, C. R., Lin, Q. Y. & Li, L. (2012). 石春让, 林庆扬 & 李琳. (2012). 基于语料库的中企简介翻译研究. [A Corpus-Based Study on the Translation of Chinese Enterprise Profiles]. 西北大学学报(哲学社会科学版) [Journal of Northwest University(Philosophy and Social Sciences Edition)], (05), 180-182.
- Sun, Q. Y. (2015). 图式理论关照下文化负载词的翻译研究 [Translation of Cultural-loaded Words in Light of Schema Theory: A Case Study of Howard Goldblatt's Translation of Feng Ru Fei Tun]. 硕士学位论文, 四川外国语大学 [Master's paper in Sichuan International Studies University].
- Tan, W. G. (2021). 《郑州宇通客车股份有限公司简介》汉译英实践报告 [Report on CE-Translation of Profile of Zhengzhou Yutong Bus CO., Ltd]. 硕士学位论文, 上海师范大学 [Master's paper in Shanghai Normal University].
- Wu, Q. R. (2009). 从顺应论角度看公司简介的翻译 [An Adaption Approach to Translation of Company Profiles]. 硕士学位论文, 湖南师范大学. [Master's paper in Hunan Normal University].
- Xu, X. C. (2020). 交际翻译视角下的茶叶公司简介英译问题分析. [A Study on the C-E Translation Problems of Tea Company Profiles from the Perspective of Communicative Translation Theory]. 福建茶叶 [Tea in Fujian], (09), 236-237.
- Yan, A. H. (2016). 基于图示理论的翻译过程研究. [A Study on Translation Process Based on Schema Theory]. 黑河学刊 [HEIHE JOURNAL], (01), 26-27.
- Yan, X. Y. (2019). 国内文化图式理论研究综述(2000—2018). [A Review of Cultural Schemata Theory in China (2000-2018)]. 湖北文理学院学报 [Journal of Hubei University of Arts and Science], (03), 66-71.
- Zheng, L. (2021). 功能对等理论指导下外向型企业简介的汉英翻译策略研究 [On the C-E Translation Strategies of Export-oriented Company Profiles from the Perspective of Functional Equivalence Theory —— Case Study of Company Profiles in Liaoning Province]. 硕士学位论文, 吉林财经大学 [Master's paper in Jilin University of Finance and Economics].
- Zhu, L. (2020). 动态对等论指导下的英汉翻译 [E-C Translation under the Guidance of the Dynamic Equivalence Theory---A Case Study of the Translation of One of Ours]. 硕士学位论文, 江西财经大学. [Master's paper in Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics].